

Multimodal Information Retrieval: Advanced NLP Techniques and Image-Based Book Search Using Text Extraction

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Abstract—Natural Language Processing (NLP) has emerged as a crucial field of study with a variety of applications across various domains. In the digital world, the amount of data generated is very huge. There arises an imperative need for the development of automated systems capable of condensing textual content efficiently. Implementing text summarization accelerates research processes, reduces reading durations, and enhances the extraction of pertinent information within specific domains. Addressing the task of Automatic Text Summarization presents an opportunity to tackle significant challenges, offering a solution that transcends manual efforts by providing concise and coherent summaries, thereby streamlining the process while saving both time and resources. Categorizing the textual data into distinct categories helps the user to manage large textual data effectively. Sentiment Analysis examines the emotion of the textual data. This paper delves into three key aspects of NLP: text summarization, sentiment analysis and classification of text. The paper also includes image based book search using text extraction. Text summarization involves condensing large volumes of text into concise summaries, aiding in information retrieval and comprehension. Sentiment analysis plays a pivotal role in understanding the sentiment of the textual data. Classification is used to categorize the textual data into different categories.

Keywords—Natural Language Processing (NLP), *txtai*, text summarization, sentiment analysis, text classification, VADER, OCR.

I. INTRODUCTION

The burgeoning field of Natural Language Processing (NLP) holds great promise in addressing real-world challenges. This study delves into the potential of NLP to analyse the textual data by leveraging various NLP applications. By adeptly processing and analyzing human language, the proposed system aims to comprehend and generate natural language content. Key NLP advancements explored include summarization, sentiment analysis and classification of text. The ultimate aim is to showcase how NLP can streamline the online experience, empowering readers to make informed decisions efficiently. This paper deals with how *txtai* is used in NLP. *txtai* is an open source python package that uses NLP and machine learning to search, summarize and analyze text. The Summary pipeline efficiently condenses textual content by employing a *text2text* model, which abstractively generates summaries of input text.

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It utilizes a summarization model to analyze blocks of text, supporting input either as a string or a list. When given a string, it returns a single summary. Alternatively, if provided with a list, it returns a list of summaries, with each summary corresponding to a block of text. This versatile approach enables streamlined summarization of text data, offering both flexibility and scalability in summarization tasks.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

Swaranjali Jugran, Ashish Kumar, Bhupendra Singh Tyagi, Mr. Vivek Ananad [1], underscore the contemporary significance of text summarization, given the proliferation of data accessible through digital platforms. The primary objective of their study is to devise an automated text summarization model employing the extractive technique, aimed at condensing texts and generating insightful summaries. They advocate for the utilization of the SpaCy library in their model, citing its departure from NLTK in employing an object-oriented methodology, treating text holistically and integrating word vectors to enhance semantic representation. This utilization of word vectors streamlines mathematical operations, positioning SpaCy as a more effective tool for the summarization process.

Ankita Sharma, Udayan Ghose [2], in their paper “Lexicon A linguistic Approach for Sentiment Classification” delve into the lexicon-based method for sentiment analysis, particularly focusing on polarity classification. This approach relies on lexicons, or dictionaries of words with associated sentiment scores, to categorize input data into either positive or negative sentiments. The paper also introduces VADER (Valence Aware Dictionary for Sentiment Reasoning), a tool that not only assigns a polarity score to text but also provides insight into the intensity of the expressed opinion. VADER assigns normalized valence scores ranging from -1 to 1, where negative valence is below 0 and -1, neutral valence is at 0, and positive valence ranges between 0 and 1.

Jasleen Kaur and Dr. Jatinderkumar R. SAINI [3] on their research titled “ A Study of Text Classification Natural Language Processing Algorithms for Indian Languages” delve into the analysis of text classification methodologies applied to Indian language content. The presence of text in Indian languages poses unique challenges for natural language processing (NLP). Their study reveals that supervised learning algorithms, including Naive Bayes (NB), Support Vector

Machine (SVM), Artificial Neural Network (ANN), and N-gram models, demonstrate superior performance in the task of text classification.

Ambarish Moharil, Shreya Singh, Yash Dravid, Harshal Dharap, along with Professor Vijaykumar Bhanuse [4], in their study titled "Integrated Feedback Analysis And Moderation Platform Using Natural Language Processing," explore sentiment analysis techniques for evaluating feedback and reviews. They emphasize the significance of preprocessing raw data before employing natural language processing and machine learning algorithms for classification. This preprocessing involves various steps such as eliminating special characters and symbols, discarding stop words, and applying techniques like stemming and lemmatization to enhance the quality of data for analysis.

Matteo Brisinello, Ratko Grbić, Dejan Stefanović, Robert Pečkai-Kovač [5], in their paper "Optical Character Recognition on images with colorful background" they propose a preprocessing method to improve the Tesseract Optical Character Recognition (OCR) performance on images with colourful backgrounds. The method involves a two-step process of text segmentation and image classification, where the text is extracted from the background and OCR is performed on the identified image. The proposed method improves Tesseract OCR performance by approximately 20%. The motivation for this paper stems from the challenges of reading text from images grabbed from set-top boxes (STBs) with complex backgrounds. The proposed method is evaluated on a set of computer-generated images, and its efficiency is compared to the standard OCR approach.

III. MOTIVATION

In today's digital world, there's a lot of data, so we need automated systems to condense text efficiently. Text summarization helps speed up research, reduce reading time, and find important information in different areas. Automatic Text Summarization is a great way to solve this problem by giving quick and clear summaries, saving time and effort. Categorizing text helps manage large amounts of data better. Sentiment Analysis looks at the emotions in text, helping us make better decisions.

IV. METHODOLOGY

A. Text Summarization

Text summarization is a process of condensing a given text document into a shorter version while retaining its key information and meaning. This paper summarises the text using the txtai's summarization pipeline. In txtai, text summarization utilizes transformer-based models like BERT or RoBERTa, pretrained on large text datasets and fine-tuned for summarization tasks. These models comprehend natural language intricacies and produce concise summaries while retaining vital information. By employing attention mechanisms, they identify key content for summarization. The resulting summaries offer condensed representations of the original text, enabling efficient comprehension of lengthy documents or articles. This approach streamlines information processing, allowing users to quickly extract essential insights from text data without compromising accuracy or relevance.

Fig. 1. Generating summary from input document.

B. Text Classification

1. Data Collection

The method utilizes the 20 newsgroup dataset from scikit-learn . This dataset comprises documents sourced from diverse newsgroups, with each document categorized into particular topics.

2. Data Preparing

Upon dataset loading, the script preprocesses the text data, converting it into numerical feature vectors through TF-IDF (Term Frequency-Inverse Document Frequency) vectorization. This process entails transforming the raw textual information into numerical representations suitable for input into the classification model.

3. Model Selection

The method opts for multinomial Naive Bayes classifier as the classification model. Naive Bayes classifiers are favoured for text classification tasks owing to their simplicity and efficiency, making them a prevalent choice in such applications.

4. Model Training

During the training phase, the Naive Bayes classifier is fitted to the vectorized text data. Throughout this process, the classifier acquires knowledge of the statistical characteristics of the input features and their correlation with the target categories, which in this case correspond to the topics covered in the newsgroup documents.

5. Classification

The input text undergoes classification using the previously trained Naive Bayes classifier. Utilizing its acquired knowledge of the dataset, the classifier then predicts the category or topic associated with the input text.

C. Sentiment Analysis

The method utilizes VADER, a pre-trained model from NLTK. It evaluates text sentiment by assigning polarity scores (positive, negative, neutral) based on the content's emotional tone. The compound score determines overall sentiment polarity, where values above 0.05 classify as positive, below -0.05 as negative, and in-between as neutral. Users receive sentiment analysis results through Streamlit interface, offering quick insights into the emotional context of the input text.

D. Book Search Using Image Recognition And OpenCV

The code employs computer vision techniques to detect books within a webcam feed. It first loads book images from a directory and then captures frames from the webcam. Each captured frame is compared against the book images using Mean Squared Error (MSE) calculation. If the MSE falls below a predefined threshold, indicating a close match, the

code determines that a book is present in the frame. This method offers a straightforward approach to real-time book detection, enabling applications such as inventory management or augmented reality book overlays.

V. Method of Implementation

A. Text Summarization

Text summarization in this implementation utilizes the txtai library's summarization pipeline. It simplifies the process by leveraging transformer-based models, enabling the generation of coherent and informative summaries with minimal effort. First, the summarization pipeline is loaded. Then, a function `text_summary(text)` is defined to generate a summary. When invoked with a piece of text, this function utilizes the loaded summarization pipeline to generate a concise summary. The txtai library employs advanced transformer-based models pre-trained on large text corpora, allowing it to understand the context and semantics of the input text and produce coherent and informative summaries while preserving essential information.

1. Import necessary packages.

```
from txtai.pipeline import Summary
from PyPDF2 import PdfReader
```

2. Initialize the text summarization pipeline

```
result = text_summary(input_text)
```

3. To summarise the input text

```
if choice == "Summarize Text":
    st.subheader("Summarize Text, Classify, and Detect Books")
    input_text = st.text_area("Enter your text here")
    if input_text is not None:
        if st.button("Analyze"):
            # Classify text
            category = classify_text(input_text)
            st.success(f"Classified Category: {category}")
```

```
# Generate summary
```

```
result = text_summary(input_text)
st.markdown("**Summary Result**")
st.success(result)
```

4. To summarise the input document

```
elif choice == "Summarize Document":
    st.subheader("Summarize Document, Classify, and Detect Books")
    input_file = st.file_uploader("Upload your document here", type=[
    if input_file is not None:
        if st.button("Analyze Document"):
            with open("doc_file.pdf", "wb") as f:
                f.write(input_file.getbuffer())
                extracted_text = extract_text_from_pdf("doc_file.pdf")
```

```
# Generate summary
```

```
doc_summary = text_summary(extracted_text)
st.markdown("**Summary Result**")
st.success(doc_summary)
```

B. Text Classification

1. Import necessary libraries and datasets

```
from sklearn.datasets import fetch_20newsgroups
from sklearn.feature_extraction.text import TfidfVectorizer
from sklearn.naive_bayes import MultinomialNB
```

2. Text classification model using TF-IDF vectorization and Multinomial Naive Bayes Algorithm.

```
vectorizer = TfidfVectorizer()
X_train = vectorizer.fit_transform(newsgroups.data)
model = MultinomialNB()
model.fit(X_train, newsgroups.target)
```

3. Categorising the text.

```
category = classify_text(input_text)
st.success(f"Classified Category: {category}")
```

C. Sentiment Analysis

Sentiment analysis in this code is performed using the VADER (Valence Aware Dictionary and sEntiment Reasoner) sentiment analysis model from NLTK (Natural Language Toolkit). The **SentimentIntensityAnalyzer** from NLTK is used to analyze the sentiment of the input text. It assigns a compound score to the text, indicating its overall sentiment polarity (positive, negative, or neutral). The compound score is then used to determine the sentiment category (positive, negative, or neutral), based on predefined thresholds.

1. Import necessary libraries

```
from nltk.sentiment.vader import SentimentIntensityAnalyzer
```

2. Load the VADER sentiment analysis model

```
# Load the VADER sentiment analysis model
sid = SentimentIntensityAnalyzer()
```

3. Analysing the sentiment.

```
# Analyze sentiment
sentiment_scores = sid.polarity_scores(input_text)
if sentiment_scores['compound'] >= 0.05:
    sentiment = "Positive"
elif sentiment_scores['compound'] <= -0.05:
    sentiment = "Negative"
else:
    sentiment = "Neutral"
st.success(f"Sentiment: {sentiment}")
```

C. Image-based book Search Using Text Extraction

Book detection involves capturing webcam frames, extracting text via OCR, and comparing it with reference book images. Each captured frame undergoes OCR to obtain text. Text similarity with book images' text is calculated using SequenceMatcher. A similarity threshold determines presence, saved frame verifies capture. If similarity exceeds the threshold (adjustable), the system confirms the book's

presence, displaying the best match. Otherwise, it concludes the absence of a book. The process leverages computer vision and text analysis to detect books in real-time webcam feeds, enabling swift identification and categorization.

1. Import necessary libraries

```
import cv2
import os
import pytesseract
from difflib import SequenceMatcher
```

2. Extract text from an image using OCR and compare with details in the database

```
# Function to load images from a directory
def load_images_from_folder(folder):
    images = []
    for filename in os.listdir(folder):
        img = cv2.imread(os.path.join(folder, filename))
        if img is not None:
            images.append(img)
    return images

# Function to extract text from an image using OCR
def extract_text(image):
    gray = cv2.cvtColor(image, cv2.COLOR_BGR2GRAY)
    text = pytesseract.image_to_string(gray, lang='eng') # Specify language
    return text.strip()

# Function to compare text similarity using SequenceMatcher
def text_similarity(text1, text2):
    return SequenceMatcher(None, text1, text2).ratio()

# Compare the captured text with the text from book images
max_similarity = 0
best_match = None
for book_img in book_images:
    book_text = extract_text(book_img)
    similarity = text_similarity(captured_text.lower(), book_text.lower())
    if similarity > max_similarity:
        max_similarity = similarity
        best_match = book_text

if best_match and max_similarity > 0.7: # Adjust similarity threshold as needed
    print("Book present!")
    print("Best match:", best_match)
else:
    print("Book not present!")

break
```

V. RESULT

The result after the research work is shown below.

Fig. 2. Output screenshot 1

Fig. 2. Output screenshot 2

Fig. 3. Output screenshot 3

VI. CONCLUSION

NLP has garnered considerable attention recently due to its effectiveness in addressing real-world problems. This paper explores the application of NLP to enhance user experience by focusing on four key areas of development: text summarization, sentiment analysis, text classification, and book search using image recognition and NLP. The primary aim is to demonstrate how NLP can help users save time and make informed decisions by efficiently processing and analyzing text data.

REFERENCES

- [1] Swaranjali Jugran, Ashish Kumar, Bhupendra Singh Tyagi, Mr. Vivek Anand "Extractive Automatic Text Summarization using SpaCy in Python & NLP" , 20 April 2021.
- [2] Ankita Sharma, Udayan Ghose "Lexicon A Linguistic Approach for Sentiment Classification" , 15 March 2021.
- [3] Jasleen Kaur, Dr. Jatinderkumar R. SAINI "A Study of Text Classification Natural Language Processing Algorithms for Indian Languages", July 2015
- [4] Ambarish Moharil, Shreya Singh, Yash Dravid, Harshal Dharap, Prof. Vijaykumar Bhanuse, "Integrated Feedback Analysis And Moderation Platform Using Natural Language Processing", 19 August 2020.Y.
- [5] Matteo Brisinello, Ratko Grbić, Dejan Stefanović, Robert Pečkai-Kovač "Optical Character Recognition on images with colorful background", 16 December 2018.